

CHARACTERIZATION OF SOME ANIMAL RESIDUES AS POTENTIAL ALTERNATIVES TO FOSSIL FUELS AND SOIL AMENDMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to perform a comparative study on some selected animal residues in order to explore their potential as alternative sources of energy and soil amendments. Agricultural residues are potential deposits and reservoir of energy vectors that could be used as renewable energy sources if harnessed for economic purposes. Average annual livestock residue in Nigeria was estimated at 105,007 Mt most of which were left without meaningful and appreciable economic viable management policy. The multiplication of livestock farming and aggravated accumulation of crop residues after harvest stimulates increased emission of greenhouse gases during decomposition and burning thereby encouraging rise in average global temperatures and increased greenhouse effect. Four livestock residues wastes were evaluated for their yield potentials of CH₄, CO₂, and N₂O at an ambient temperature (28°C). Both physical and chemical compositions of the residues were determined using standard laboratory procedures after drying at 77°C. Percent by mass (Pm), molar compositions (Mc); molar ratios (Mr.), air requirements for oxidation (Ar), chemical formulae (Cf), energy content (Ec) and potential volume of methane (Pv) available for harvest were evaluated using empirical models. Results obtained showed that poultry manure has the highest percentage of CH₄ (15.51%); pig has the highest percentage of CO₂ (16.62%); the N obtained for all the manures were similar, while the N₂O was insignificant to make any meaningful difference. The results also shows that, horse manure has the highest percentage of 8.03% K while the amount of N, and P are similar for all the manures tested, suggesting suitable alternative composting sources for soil amendment. Overall result shows that poultry manure has the best potential energy value of 45.852 Kj/Kg.

KEYWORDS: Characterization,

1. INTRODUCTION

The potential alternative energy sources for the rural agricultural sector are biomass. Enormous volumes of agricultural wastes in form of livestock manure, crop residues, agro-industrial wastes and human excreta are littered in the environment causing severe environmental pollution. If properly managed, such residues could be converted into potential sources of energy that could be ploughed back into agricultural production and processing activities (Onyema, 2010).

Applying animal residues as alternative source of inorganic fertilizers has gradually declined due to several factors. Primarily, cattle rustling, separation of crop and livestock production, and increased availability and dependence on synthetic fertilizers were the influencing factors (Akyurek, 2018). Studies have shown that besides polluting the environment, use of commercially available synthetic fertilizers degrade the quality of the soil overtime (Akyurek, 2018). The increasing effects of synthetic fertilizers and improperly treated animal wastes on the environment and human health made researches on alternative source of energy and soil amendments inevitable (Demirbas, 2009). Animal residues are known for supplying nutrients for crop production and organic matter which in turn improves soil structure, water holding capacity,

drainage, reduces wind and water erosion, provides a source of slow release nutrients, and promotes growth of earthworms and valuable microbes for crop production (Akyurek, 2018). Animal residues have been considered as a potential fertilizer throughout the millennia. Such residues were known to contain essential macro- and micro-nutrients for crop effective growth and as a cost-effective alternative to inorganic fertilizers. They also have various uses such as fuel source, disinfectant, purifier, insects repellent (Demirbas, 2009).and a valuable feed for earthworms in vermicomposting process (George and Frank, 2002 and Howard *et al.*, 1985). The relationship between the feed and the animal excreta has been established by many researchers (Isci and Demirer, 2007; Gerrit, 2020; Kashyap *et al.*, 2003 and Sujatha and Alison, 2014). The properties of such residues depend on several factors: animal species; diet, digestibility, protein and fiber content; and animal age, housing, environment, and stage of production.

Previous studies shows that animal residues can be transformed into resources for composting or soil amendments in crop production, raw materials for industrial operations and energy generation when adequately and sustainably harnessed. Tchnobanoglous *et al.* (2002) opined that the most effective way of managing animal residues is by reducing of the amount and the toxicity entrenched. Interestingly, as people search for better life and higher standard of living, more products are consumed with resultant higher degree of waste generation. Notwithstanding the perceived menace and potentials of the animal residues, more complex resolution were required before concerted efforts are put in place for their utilization. Available literatures on the use of animal residues for energy production in Nigeria (especially biogas energy) compared the potentials of other animal residues with energy crops in terms of C/N ratio (George, and Frank, 2002). Most animal residues still remained the most untapped bio fuel (Akyurek, 2018, Isci and Demirer, 2007). Conventionally, the annual average amount of livestock residue in Nigeria was estimated at 105,007 Mt without adding significant national economic viable management policy for utilization. This study is aimed at characterizing the potentials of some selected livestock residues (Cow, Horse, Poultry and Pig) as viable alternative sources of energy and soil amendments for the rural household and enhanced crop production.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in the Processing Laboratory of the Department of Agricultural and Bio-Resources Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Samaru-Zaria. Samaru lies within latitude 11°11'N and longitude 7°38'E at an altitude of about 686m above mean sea level. The climatic condition of Samaru is characterized by an annual mean rainfall of 1000 mm, atmospheric humidity as low as 15% during the dry season and above 60% during the wet season. The minimum and maximum temperatures of 22°C in January and 28°C in the month of April (Akhtar *et al.*, 2013).

Four livestock residues components comprising Cow, Horse, Poultry droppings and Pig wastes were collected within Samaru and evaluated for their yield potentials of CH₄, CO₂, and N₂O at ambient temperature. Moisture content of the livestock residues expressed as the mass of moisture per unit dry material was obtained by drying in an oven at (Heraeus/Hanau) at 60°C for 12 h to a constant weight and their respective moisture contents were determined using Equation (1) as suggested by Ekebafe *et al.* (2012):

$$Mc (\%) = \frac{W_{sbd} - W_{sad}}{W_{sad}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where,

Mc = Moisture Content, %;

W_{sbd} = Weight of Sample before drying, g;

W_{sad} = Weight of Sample after drying, g

Both proximate and ultimate compositions of the samples were determined using standard laboratory procedures to determine the level of nitrogen and carbon concentrations obtainable for possible composting after digestion for methane production. Percent by mass, molar composition, molar ratio were determined based on the model developed by Howard *et al.* (1985). Appropriate chemical formula with or without sulphur was obtained based on the ratio of the molar mass of each sample to the moles of sulphur and nitrogen where the moles were calculated on the mass of each element to the atomic mass of the sample. Energy content of samples were determined using Dulong formula:

$$\text{kJ/kg} = 337C + 1428(H-0/8) + 9S \quad (2)$$

where,

C = Carbon,

H = Hydrogen,

O = Oxygen

S = Sulphur percent.

Energy content was evaluated using equation (3) as kJ/kg (ash-free dry basis) =

$$\text{kJ/kg (as discarded)} \left[\frac{100}{100 - \% \text{ ash} - \% \text{ mc}} \right] \quad (3)$$

where mc is percent moisture content, assuming the ash content is = 5.0% (Howard *et al.*, 1985). The samples' moisture contents were converted to hydrogen and oxygen following the computation model of Howard *et al.* (1985). The chemical formulae of the samples were determined based on the conversion trend with and without sulphur.

Air requirements for complete oxidation of one tonne of each sample were calculated using equation (iv) based on the chemical compounds estimated.

where a, b, c and d are coefficients of C.H.O. and N.

The overall anaerobic conversion of organic wastes occurring in three phases such as liquefaction, bacterial conversion into lower molecular weight intermediate compounds and bacterial conversion of the intermediate compounds into end products like CO₂ and CH₄ was expressed by equation (5) as:

where, $s = a - nw - m$; $r = c - ny - 2s$ with the assumption of complete conversion to CO₂ and CH₄ (Howard *et al.*, 1985). Potential volume of methane gas expected from the anaerobic digestion of a tonne of samples based on equation (6) was determined using as:

where a, b, c and d are co-efficient assuming 0.7167 kgm⁻³ and 0.85 as the density of methane and actual volume of gas for production respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results for the chemical composition of the selected livestock samples are presented in Table 1. The degree of variation in composition is very minimal possibly showing residues of similar soil amendments potentials. However, C/N ratio shows 33:1, 37:1, 28:1 and 28:1 for Hs, Cw, Po and Pg respectively confirming the superiority of Po and Pg over other livestock residues in terms of C/N ratio in contrast to the report of Akyurek, 2018, Isci and Dermirer (2007), which could be attributed to the variation in C content. Similarly, Hs recorded the least C concentration and next to the lowest H⁺ (Table 1), while Po with the highest moisture content dry basis, produced the highest H⁺, showing the greatest possibility of aerobic digestion of methane, the highest potential for fertilizer in terms of percent N and next in evolution of S to Pg. Table 2 presents the mass and percent by mass components of the combined livestock residues when mixed together.

Table 1. Composition of some livestock residues

Livestock	Dry mass used for analysis (kg)	C H O N S MC					
		C H O N S MC (%)					
Horse	0.05	0.99	0.103	0.062	0.03	0.037	13.87
Cow	0.05	1.12	0.098	0.056	0.03	0.0194	17.03
Poultry	0.05	1.12	0.130	0.070	0.04	0.030	35.25
Pig	0.05	1.12	0.112	0.06	0.04	0.044	4.98

Table 2. Composition of the cumulative components of some residues

Component	Mass (kg)	Percent by mass (%)
Moisture	69.13	-
C	4.35	5.9
H	0.443	11.0
O	1.310	83.0
N	0.14	0.19
S	0.13	0.18

Oxygen exhibited the highest percent by mass which possibly suggests the presence of stoichiometric amount of oxygen required for combustion of the residues. Tables 3 and 4 show the molar compositions and molar ratios of the residues under combined formulation with the chemical formulae with or without sulphur as C₉₀H₂₀₁₀O₉₆₀S_{1.0} and C₃₆H₈₀₄O₃₈₄N_{1.0}. Similarly, Table 5 reflects the percent by mass of the individual livestock residue showing Po as the highest in C, H, O, N and Pg the highest in S concentrations respectively. Both the molar compositions and the molar ratios of each livestock residues are shown in Tables 6 and 7. The values were not consistent as Cw gave the highest for C, Hs, for H⁺, Po for O and Hs for S. This trend is however

expected in view of the different nutrient dynamics typical of the rations specific to different livestock. However, based on the molar ratio without sulphur, the chemical formulae evaluated for Hs, Cw, Po and Pg were Hs = C_{38.1} H_{49.0} O_{1.91} N; Cw = C_{42.9} H_{44.8} O_{15.2} N; Po = C₃₁ H_{44.8} O_{15.2} N and Pg = C₃₁ H_{38.6} O_{1.3} N respectively with Hs exhibiting the highest H⁺ followed by Cw and Pg the least (Table 8). The theoretical air requirement to completely oxidize one ton of both combined livestock residues and individual residues are shown in Tables 9 and 10 with the assumption of percent oxygen in the air as 23.13%, density of air as 1.2928kgm⁻³, density of methane as 0.7167kgm⁻³ and the actual value due to synthesis of cell tissue as 0.85 (Howard *et al*, 1985). Although, the theoretical cumulative energy values generated by the individual residues was 55.6 percent greater than the combined. However, the theoretical air requirements to completely oxidize one ton of the individual residues were correspondingly 15.6% higher than the combined. Similarly, the theoretical volume of methane expected under the combined formulation was 66.4 m³t⁻¹ compared with 3,547.2 m³t⁻¹ observed in the cumulative addition of individual residues.

Table 3. Molar compositions of the different components

Components	Mass (kg)	kg/mol	Moles
C	4.35	12.01	0.36
H	8.12	1.01	8.04
O	61.45	16.0	3.84
N	0.14	14.01	0.01
S	0.13	32.06	0.004

Table 4. Mole ratios of the different components

Element	Sulfur	Nitrogen
C	90.0	36.0
H	2010	804
O	960	384
N	2.5	1.0
S	1.0	0.4

Table 5. Percent by mass of the different elements in the livestock waste

Waste	C		H		O		N		S	
	mass (kg)	% by mass	mass (kg)	% by mass	mass (kg)	% by mass	mass (kg)	% by mass	mass (kg)	% by mass
Horse	0.99	22.75	0.13	23.3	0.062	25.0	0.03	21.4	0.037	28.46
Cow	1.12	25.75	0.098	22.1	0.056	22.6	0.03	21.4	0.019	14.62
Poultry	1.12	25.75	0.130	29.3	0.070	28.2	0.04	28.6	0.030	23.08
Pig	1.12	25.75	0.112	25.3	0.060	24.2	0.04	28.6	0.044	33.85
Total	4.35	100	0.47	100	0.248	100	0.14	100	0.13	100

Table 6. Molar compositions of the elements in livestock wastes

Waste	C	Kg/mol	mole	H	Kg/mol	mole	O	Kg/mol	mole	N	Kg/mol	mol	S	Kg/mol	mole
Horse	0.99	12.01	0.08	0.103	1.01	0.103	0.062	16.0	0.0040	0.03	14.01	0.0021	0.037	32.06	0.0012
Cow	1.12	12.01	0.09	0.098	1.01	0.098	0.056	16.0	0.0035	0.03	14.01	0.0021	0.019	32.06	0.0006
Poultry	1.12	12.01	0.09	0.130	1.01	0.130	0.070	16.0	0.0044	0.04	14.01	0.0029	0.030	32.06	0.009
Pig	1.12	12.01	0.09	0.112	1.01	0.112	0.060	16.0	0.0038	0.04	14.01	0.0029	0.044	32.06	0.0014

Table 7. Molar ratios of the elements in livestock residues without sulfur

Residue-	C		H		O		N		S	
	C	MR	H	MR	O	MR	N	MR	S	MR
Horse	0.08	38.1	0.103	49.05	0.004	1.9	0.0021	1.0	0.012	0
Cow	0.09	42.9	0.098	46.7	0.0035	1.7	0.0021	1.0	0.006	0
Poultry	0.09	31.0	0.130	44.8	0.044	15.2	0.0029	1.0	0.009	0
Pig	0.09	31.0	0.112S	38.6	0.0038	1.3	0.0029	1.0	0.0014	0

Table 8. Chemical Formulae

Horse	-	$C_{38.1}H_{49.0}O_{1.91}N$
Cow	-	$C_{42.9}H_{46.7}O_{1.7}N$
Poultry-		$C_{31}H_{44.8}O_{15.2}N$
Pig	-	$C_{31}H_{38.6}O_{1.3}N$

Table 9. Air requirements to oxidize completely 1 tonne of combined Horse, Cow, Pig and Poultry waste with chemical equation $C_{36}H_{804}O_{384}N_{1.0}$

Mass of air required	Vol. of air required	Oxygen required	Mass of methane	Vol.
kg/t	m ³ /t	kg/t	kg/t	m ³ /t
3327.9	2573.78	770.29	47.6	66.4

Table 10. Air requirements to oxidize completely 1 tonne of livestock Residues and methane production

Residue	Mass of Air reqd.	Vol of Air reqd.	Oxygen required	Mass of methane	Vol. of methane
	kg/t	m ³ /t	kg/t	kg/t	m ³ /t
Horse	12,713.6	9,834.14	2943.19	706.74	986.10
Cow	12,553.74	9,710.5	2906.19	719.9	1,004.5
Poultry	14,000	10,830	3,240	410.5	572.7
Pig	12,755.5	9,866.6	2952.9	705.2	983.9

Generally, the mass of air required for the production of methane was highest under Pg and lowest under Hs. Correspondingly, the theoretical volume of methane produced was highest under Cw with the lowest mean volume of air while the highest energy value was obtained under Po at 45,852.0kj/kg (Table 11). However, it is interesting to observe that ionic number of carbon and oxygen in the chemical formula of the residues played a significant role in potential volume of methane obtainable for production. Cw with chemical formula $C_{42.9} H_{44.8} O_{15.2} N$ exhibiting the highest ionic number of carbon and oxygen recorded the highest volume of methane. Overall

result suggests that Cw was more preferable for methane production among the livestock residues investigated, although, in terms of energy value, Po appeared the best.

Table 11. Energy content (Heating value) of the livestock wastes

Residue	Energy content kj/kg
Horse	35,179.2
Cow	36,350.7
Poultry	45,852.0
Pig	41,031.05

4. CONCLUSION

Livestock residue keep increasing on daily basis which suggests a positive correlation between livestock and waste accumulation. Increased agricultural activities in livestock husbandries encourage aggravated increase of leachates, effluents and solid wastes with life threatening and toxic build-up because the resultant wastes are left to decompose freely with evolution of greenhouse gases. Therefore, the greater the accumulation of these gases without conversion to useful products, the greater the tendency for more heats than needed to be trapped thereby making the earth less comfortable for humans, plants and animals. Moreover, climate effect and the attendant issues that seem to defile solution in addition to consistently diminishing natural resources like fossil fuels, surface and underground water pose a great danger to local, national and international survival.

REFERENCES

- Akhtar, S., S. Shakeel, A. Mehmood, A. Hamid and S. Saif, (2013). Comparative analysis of animal manure for soil condition. *International Journal of Agronomy and Plant Production*, 4(12): 3360-3365
- Akyurek Z. (2018). Potential of biogas energy from animal wastes in the Mediterranean region of turkey. *Journal of energy systems*. Vol. 2 No. 4, 160-167. <https://doi.org/10.30521/jes.455325>
- Demirbas, A. (2009). Biofuels securing the planet's future energy needs. *Energy conservation and management*. Vol. 50 No.9. pp 2239-2249. Doi.10.1016/j.encoman.2009.05.010.
- Ekebafé, M.O., P.O. Oviasogie, E. Oko-Oboh and L.O. Ekebafé, (2012). Effect of organic waste amendments on the pH of soil supporting the oil palm. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 1(4): 239-245.
- Erguclenler, A and Isigun, A. (1994). Agricultural residues as a potential resource for environmentally sustainable electric power generation in Turkey. *Renewable energy*, vol. 5 (5-8): 786-790.
- George, T. and Frank, K. (2002). Handbook of Solid waste Management 2nd Edition. Mc Graw-Hill companies New Delhi. pp 1-834.
- Gerrit, J. E (2020). Co-digestion of cow and sheep manure: Performance evaluation and relative microbial activity. *Renewable Energy*, Vol. 1:53, pp 553-563.
- Howard, S.P. Donald, R.R. and George, T. (1985). Environmental Engineering, McGraw – Hill Book Company, Sydney. Pp 1-698.

- Isci, A. and Demirer, C.N. (2007). Biogas production from cotton wastes. *Renewable Energy*, vol.32 (5): 780-757.
- Kashyap, D.R., Dadhich, K.S. and Sharma, S.K. (2003). Biomethanation underpsychrophilic conditions: a review. *Bioresource Technology*, Vol. 87(2): 147-153.
- Onyema, M. C. (2010). Alternative energy sources for agricultural production and processing in Nigeria. *International Food Policy Research Institute*. No. 24. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.3749.7683ER
- Sujatha, R. and Alison M. (2014). Biofuels and the role of space in sustainable innovation journeys. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. vol. 65, pp 224 – 233.
- Tchobanoglous, G., Theisen, H and Eliassen, R. (2002). *Solid Wastes: Engineering Principles and Management Issues*, McGraw-Hill, New York.